

Forest Restoration and Regeneration with Biodiverse Plantations

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Forest restoration after a forest fire in Galicia (NW Spain), as part of the LIFE-VAIA project

Forest restoration after fires is a really important issue to restore the forest and derived provision, cultural and environmental ecosystem services. The fire intensity affects the resilience capacity of the soil. Big fires affecting larger areas usually completely destroy topsoil health on the topsoil while prescribed or controlled burning may enhance soil fertility. Moreover, the type of existing forest species in the fired area causes a differentiation in the soil restoration. Natural restoration is faster in areas that were formerly occupied by broadleaves than by conifers, which increases the broadleaves value to facilitate the restoration after a big fire and therefore the long-term resilience of the forest stand. Once a fire is happening, understanding which are the species that has to be used is essential to restore the former habitats considering agroecological principles linked to the use of biodiversity in a successional and temporal scale. For this purpose, a restoration was established under the project LIFE-VAIA with 10 species that has to consider not only the capacity to grow but the climate change.

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Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.